

ENHANCING THE INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF ENTERPRISES OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001179>

Abstract. *This article discusses the pathways for improving the mechanisms aimed at increasing the innovative activity of enterprises within the construction materials industry.*

Keywords: *enterprise, construction materials industry, innovation, mechanism, production, Global Innovation Index rating, strategy.*

It is essential for enterprises to possess a high level of innovative activity to effectively fulfill their socio-economic mission and objectives, as well as to ensure sustainable development. This indicates that the innovative activity of enterprises within construction materials industry is primarily contingent upon the effectiveness of the state's policies in the innovation sector, which is also reflected in the operational mechanisms of the national innovation system.

As it is known, the mission of an enterprise is the long-term strategic directions for the development of its activities. The mission of an enterprise in the construction materials industry can be understood as the sum of its strengths and characteristics that can ensure its success in the market. The mission of the enterprise of construction materials industry, in turn, is a platform for setting strategic goals, which determines the general vector of development of its activities and allows choosing the right priorities. The effectiveness of innovation processes at enterprises is achieved by increasing the level of innovative activity, its organization and mechanisms. To do this, it is necessary to develop medium-term and long-term strategies that ensure the implementation of innovative activities at enterprises. Of course, the state policy in the innovation sphere depends on the interorganizational corporate ties of science, education and production and the level of synergistic effect they receive.

Based on the mentioned above, on September 21, 2018, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5544 "On approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021" was adopted. In this decree, an important condition for the rapid development of the country is the rapid introduction of modern innovative technologies in the economic sectors, social and other spheres with the widespread use of scientific and technological achievements.

The existence of problems in the development of the national innovation system in the country in recent years has negatively affected the full participation of Uzbekistan in the Global Innovation Index rating compiled by prestigious and authoritative international organizations. That is why the above-mentioned decree sets the task of achieving the inclusion of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Global Innovation Index rating among 50 advanced countries of the world by 2030. To do this, it is necessary not only to implement the government's innovation policy in the country, improve its institutional aspects, but also to carry out systematic work in this area at enterprises. Therefore, in this research, when forming the innovative activity of enterprises in the construction materials industry, the task is set to increase the efficiency of innovative, managerial and potential activities and develop scenarios for its development. Because the innovative activity

of the enterprises of country's construction materials industry is determined by the presence of the following problems:

- Slowness of modernization and diversification processes at the enterprises of construction materials industry of the country;
- lack of innovative and investment projects implemented in the activities of enterprises in the construction industry;
- Works on the improvement of the competitiveness of products manufactured by enterprises of construction materials industry and expanding the range of products is not systematically implemented at the required level;
- lack of uniform indicators for assessing the innovative activity of construction enterprises;
- The fact that a national rating system assessing the level of economic and innovative development of enterprises of construction materials industry has not yet been developed;
- Lack of flexible innovative strategies aimed at medium- and long-term development of priority areas that respond to the emergence of global economic threats and the rapid growth of the technological revolution in the construction industry;
- Lack of qualified specialists developing scenarios aimed at the systematic development of innovative activities at large construction enterprises;
- Underdevelopment of mechanisms for the systemic functioning of mutually beneficial cooperation relations with enterprises and scientific institutions and the higher education system in the construction industry.

We can say that to solve the above problems, it is necessary to implement the following:

Firstly, to develop ties between enterprises of the building materials industry and entities carrying out scientific, research and experimental activities to conduct research and experimental construction work;

Secondly, to evaluate the management process, conduct business on market principles and adapt the management apparatus to the specifics of each enterprise of the construction materials industry;

Thirdly, to find the most optimal solution to current and strategic problems of innovative development by clearly defining management tasks;

Fourthly, to develop programs, operational and strategic plans aimed at developing innovative processes in accordance with the goals of enterprises of the construction materials industry;

Fifthly, to develop the construction clusters rapidly based on the extensive development of mutual cooperation of enterprises of the construction materials industry;

Sixth, to provide ample opportunities for importing new technologies, information and communication devices, means of production and modern management methods from foreign countries;

Seventh, to provide short-term training for young qualified specialists in developed foreign countries in order to establish production of goods and services that meet international standards;

Eighth, to develop economic, financial, organizational, managerial and legal means of state assistance in implementing programs related to the development and implementation of the national construction system.

Based on the results of the research and analysis, innovative activity is expressed as the sum of various resources, taking into account financial, intellectual, scientific, technical and other

resources necessary for the implementation of material production at the enterprise. Further strengthening of the efforts undertaken in Uzbekistan to modernize the economy is characterized by ensuring continuity and increasing the scale of innovative processes in the construction sector. This means that the efficiency of enterprises in the construction materials industry is determined by the introduction of developments, inventions and projects based on scientific achievements, the release of products with high scientific potential. According to these approaches, innovation activity is a set of all socio-economic systemic tools that provide access to various resources and in one way or another help participants in economic activity. Based on the stated research objective, the strategy for developing innovation activity of an enterprise in the construction materials industry consists of the following stages: - defining the strategic goals and objectives of the enterprise; - comprehensive analysis of the current state of the enterprise; - developing organizational and practical measures to implement the strategy. It is known from the experience of foreign companies that setting specific goals when developing a strategy for forming innovative activity and developing production activities in joint-stock companies allows increasing the efficiency of activities. These goals are shown in Figure 3.5.

The main goal of the strategy for forming innovative activity of an enterprise is to ultimately receive high profits and take a high position in the local and global markets. To implement innovation and investment projects at enterprises in the building materials industry and achieve stable economic growth, it is necessary to ensure political and macroeconomic stability in the country. Only then will local and foreign investors be able to guarantee long-term investments in production. Another important strategic goal of the enterprise is the existence of legal principles and their implementation. Because the interests of enterprises in the construction materials industry are ensured only through legal mechanisms. The following goals are economic, social, environmental, scientific and technical, as well as goals related to adaptation to market requirements.

Forecast of indicators of innovative activity of enterprises in the construction materials industry

Indicators	Standard level	2023	Option	Forecast by years	2023 compared to 2028, in %
				2027	
JSC "NANROB MOBILE SYSTEMS"					
Financial activity	min 1,2	1,16	1	1,64	141,4
			2	1,94	167,3
			3	2,12	182,8
Production activity	min 1	1,3	1	1,83	140,8
			2	1,32	101,5
			3	1,54	118,5
Marketing activity	min 1,3	1,4	1	1,92	137,1
			2	1,32	94,3
			3	1,52	108,6
Managerial activity	min 1,5	1,4	1	1,83	130,7
			2	1,31	93,6
			3	1,52	108,6

Labor activity	min 1	1,2	1	1,24	103,3
			2	1,53	127,5
			3	1,71	142,5
OOO "MULTI-SET BUSINESS"					
Financial activity	min 1,2	0,98	1	1,52	155,1
			2	1,94	197,9
			3	2,12	216,3
Production activity	min 1	1,4	1	1,23	87,8
			2	1,52	108,6
			3	1,83	130,7
Marketing activity	min 1,3	1,4	1	1,32	94,2
			2	1,41	100,7
			3	1,73	123,6
Managerial activity	min 1,5	1,4	1	1,24	88,6
			2	1,32	94,3
			3	1,51	107,8
Labor activity	min 1	0,7	1	1,22	174,3
			2	1,64	234,3
			3	1,82	260,0

In the implementation of this scientific forecast, by determining the trend of change in factors affecting the results, the research examines the economic indicators of the enterprises of the construction materials industry JSC "NANROB MOBILE SYSTEM" and LLC "KOP TARMOQLI BIZNES". The dynamics of changes and its forecast indicators until 2028 have been developed.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to increase the innovative activity of enterprises of the construction materials industry, it is possible to achieve its economic and social sustainable development by forecasting the growth of levels of innovative activity at enterprises of the construction industry, as well as the modernization and diversification of production of enterprises of the construction materials industry.

Based on the scientific study of these problems, the following scientific and practical conclusions were made:

- it is necessary to mention the functions of planning, consulting and decision-making, organization, coordination, risk, motivation, that is, stimulation, control, regulation, evaluation, as a function of increasing the innovative activity of enterprises of the construction materials industry.

Based on this, it is necessary to correctly use the functions of increasing the innovative activity of enterprises of the construction materials industry, including financial, production, labor, innovation and investment, management and potential activities; - a number of models and structural schemes have been developed for a comprehensive assessment of the qualitative directions related to the innovative activities of enterprises in the construction materials industry, the organization of their activities and the transparency of the innovative activities of enterprises.

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